

Determination of Tin in Low Grade Ores by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy†

N. K. ROY*, A. K. DAS and S. BANERJEE

Geological Survey of India, 27 J L Nehru Road,
Calcutta-700 016

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APLICATION of atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) to tin analysis has not met with much success. The highly resistant nature of cassiterite mineral makes the sample decomposition difficult and the poor AAS sensitivity of tin limits its application to low-tin samples. There are several reports on aas determination of tin employing mineral decomposition by ammonium iodide volatilisation^{1,2}. All these methods, however, employ sample decomposition under reflux conditions which is not suitable for routine applications.

The present paper describes a method employing a very simple decomposition technique involving ammonium iodide volatilisation followed by solvent extraction for concentration of tin iodide complex by trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO)—methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) mixture.

Experimental

Standard tin solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving metallic tin (99.9% purity) in 50% (v/v) HCl (A.R.). Further dilutions were made as necessary before use. Hydrochloric acid strength of about 1 N was uniformly maintained. All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. TOPO—MIBK reagent (4%) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of TOPO in MIBK.

A Perkin-Elmer 303 atomic absorption spectrometer with Fisher hollow cathode lamp was used. All measurement were made in N₂O—acetylene flame.

Procedure: Powdered mineral sample (0.5 g) was mixed with ammonium iodide (4.0 g) in a hard glass test tube. The mixture was placed in an air-oven at 110° for ~1 h and then cooled to room temperature. The upper portion of the test tube was wrapped with a piece of cloth soaked in cold water and the tube heated over a low flame for 15 min avoiding heating of the upper portion of the tube. The tube was cooled to room temperature and 1 N HCl (10 ml) of 5% ascorbic acid (5ml) were added so carefully that the sublimate at the upper part of the test tube was carried down to the bottom. The test tube was placed in a boiling water bath and the lumps, if any, were broken with a glass rod. The mixture was cooled, transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask and the

volume was made with 0.5 N HCl. An aliquot containing not more than 50 µg of tin was transferred from the clear supernate into a small separatory funnel and diluted to about 50 ml with 0.5 N HCl. TOPO—MIBK reagent (5 ml) was then added to it and shaken vigorously for 30 s. The layers were then allowed to separate. The organic phase was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The dry organic phase was aspirated into nitrous oxide—acetylene flame for atomic absorption measurement.

The calibration curves, were constructed using different known values of standard tin solution (10 µg Sn/ml) and processed as before.

Results and Discussion

The proposed method has been applied to the determination of tin in a number of cassiterite bearing rock samples and the results (Table 1) are

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF AAS DETERMINATION OF TIN SAMPLES

Sample no	Present method Sn% (Found)	XRF method Sn% (Found)
1	0.07	0.07
2	0.15	0.14
3	0.27	0.26
4	0.95	0.90
5	3.20	3.10
6	6.01	5.99
7	9.21	9.10
8	0.05	0.05*

*Recommended value for CANMET

in good agreement with those obtained by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry. Recoveries of tin has been tested by analysing a synthetic mixture (SiO₂, 70; Fe₂O₃, 10; Al₂O₃, 10; CaO 5; MgO, 5%) with addition of 50 µg of tin to each. Recoveries ranging 97.6–99.7% have been obtained with relative standard deviation of 6.5. One standard reference sample for CANMET (MP-2) has also been analysed by the method (Table 1). The method is practically free from chemical interferences because most of the major elements get separated during the sample decomposition operation. Metals like Cu, Pb, Sb, Bi, Hg which may form iodide complex under similar conditions may cause interference, if present in large amount (above 1%), but such large concentration of these elements are rarely expected in cassiterite samples. The proposed method may be applied to cassiterite bearing samples having 0.01 to 10% Sn.

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4-(2-Pyridylazo)naphthol—An Amperometric Reagent for Trace Determination of Gallium(III), Indium(III) and Thallium(I)

RIYAZ AHMAD and K. S. PITRE*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

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AMONG the various heterocyclic azo dyes¹⁻⁴, PAN, PAR and TAR have been satisfactorily used for the spectrophotometric determination of rare earths. Recently in our laboratory, current-voltage behaviour of such azo dyes has been investigated and the dyes used as amperometric reagents⁵⁻⁸. The spectrophotometric method is not suitable when precipitation occurs, nor it can be used at the close proximity of the wavelength of adsorption of complex and ligand. The present paper deals with the use of 4-(2-pyridylazo)naphthol (PAN) for the trace determination of the titled metal ions. The method is fairly sensitive and accurate.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR or extrapure quality. Solutions of metal ions, viz. Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the metal nitrate in double-distilled water and standardised by EDTA⁹. The solution of PAN was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the reagent in double-distilled water. Amperometric titrations were performed on a manually operated polarograph with a multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1 × 10⁻⁹ A/div), used to measure the current. A d.m.e. and a saturated

calomel electrode were used as an indicator and reference electrode, respectively. The capillary used for d.m.e. had a value of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.316 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$. The amperometric titrations were performed at room temperature 30 ± 1°. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used to measure the pH of the test solutions.

Polarographic behaviour of metal ions: Each of the Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I gave a very well defined reduction wave in 0.1 M KCl at pH 4.0 + 0.02. The diffusion current for each wave is proportional to the concentration of the metal. PAN did not give any wave under the said experimental conditions.

For titrations, sets of solutions containing known amount of PAN in 0.3 M KCl as supporting electrolyte were prepared and pH of each set was adjusted to 4.0 ± 0.02. The titrations with each of the metal ions as titrant were carried out separately at -0.6 V vs S.C.E. in case of In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I, and at -1.20 V vs S.C.E. with Ga⁺⁺⁺, respectively (the mentioned potentials being the plateau potentials of respective reduction waves of In⁺⁺⁺, Tl^I and Ga⁺⁺⁺) Reversed L-shaped curves were obtained on plotting galvanometer deflection against the volume of titrant added. The end-point indicated metal-PAN ratio of 1:2 in each case. The L-shaped curves may be obtained using the metal solution as titrate and PAN as titrant.

Results and Discussion

The titrations were not hampered by the presence of various foreign ions viz. chloride, iodide, acetate, nitrate, chlorate, sulphate, Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Mg⁺⁺ and Ca⁺⁺ etc. However, a small amount of carbonate, phosphate, Cu⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺, Ni⁺⁺, Pd⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺⁺, Sb⁺⁺⁺, and rare earths etc. seriously interfered the titration procedure.

The results of amperometric estimations of the titled metal ions with PAN are presented in Table 1. The results indicate that the PAN is a good amperometric reagent for the trace determination of Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I. Amounts as low as 69.85 ppm of Ga⁺⁺⁺, 114.8 ppm of In⁺⁺⁺ and 204.3 ppm

TABLE —AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ AND Tl^I WITH PAN

Plateau potential = -1.20 V vs S.C.E. with Ga⁺⁺⁺, -0.65 V vs S.C.E. with In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I
I = 0.3 M (KCl), pH = 4.0 + 0.02, Temp. = 30 ± 1°

Sl no.	Amount of Ga ⁺⁺⁺ (ppm)			Amount of In ⁺⁺⁺ (ppm)			Amount of Tl ^I (ppm)		
	Taken	Found	% Error	Taken	Found	% Error	Taken	Found	% Error
1.	69.72	69.82	+0.18	114.8	115.8	+0.87	204.3	204.5	+0.098
2.	174.20	173.00	-0.69	287.00	286.2	-0.27	510.7	512.5	-0.35
3.	348.50	346.00	-0.71	574.00	576.8	+0.48	1 021.5	1 029.6	+0.86
4.	512.70	516.80	+0.80	861.00	860.0	-0.12	1 531.1	1 536.9	+0.47
5.	697.20	693.00	-0.60	1 148.00	1 150.0	+0.17	2 045.7	2 042.0	-0.18
6.	1 045.70	1 049.00	+0.31	1 722.00	1 718.0	-0.23	3 065.0	3 065.0	+0.23

Standard deviation (%): Ga, 0.045; In, 0.05; Tl, 0.088.
Coefficient of variation: Ga, 0.64; In, 0.43; Tl, 0.45.